

EFFECT OF SCHOOL LOCATION AND GENDER ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS STUDENTS TAUGHT AGRICULTURAL SCIENCE USING INQUIRY METHOD IN ADAMAWA STATE

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Abstract

The study determined the effect of schools' location on academic performance of senior Secondary School Students Taught Agricultural Science using Inquiry Method in Adamawa State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted pretest-posttest quasi-experimental design. The population of the study was 115,497 students in Senior Secondary Schools (SSS II) The sample size for this study was 20 intact classes, four schools in each zone, which consist of 769 Senior Secondary School (SSS II) Students (416 males and 353 females; 425 Urban and 344 Rural; 390 Inquiry and 379 lecture) who offer Agricultural Science subjects in Gombi, Numan, Mubi and Yola Education Zones of Adamawa State. The instrument for data collection in this study was "Agricultural Science Performance Test" (ASPT) developed by the researcher. The instrument was validated by three experts and a reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha method. Mean was used to answer the two research questions while ANCOVA was used test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level significance. Findings of the study revealed that there is significant difference between the mean performance scores of urban and rural agricultural science students taught using inquiry method in favour of urban students and there is a positive mean difference between the mean performance scores of male and female agricultural science students taught using inquiry method in favour of the females. The study recommended among others that urban and rural schools should organize workshops and seminars internally to enable teachers and their students share ideas on the skills of inquiry teaching method.

Keywords: School Location, Gender, Inquiry Method, Academic Performance, Agricultural Science

Introduction

Agricultural Science is one of the core subjects taught in senior secondary schools in Nigeria because of its promising role in promoting self-reliance through the provision of employment opportunities and production of staple foods for the populace together with raw material supply for the agro-allied industries, its teaching as a course offering in our schools and colleges has been made compulsory by the federal government. Agricultural science requires the application of effective and efficient method(s), skills and attitude. This is in order to make the learning of agricultural science real and practical for students and to increase students' interest and participation in agriculture both when still in school and when they must have left school. The above objectives can only be attainable through effective instruction and motivation of students by teachers of agriculture.

From the view point of Terngu, it is a strong index that unqualified teachers may not be conversant with pedagogical methodology and this may have contributed to the usage of inappropriate/unsuitable methods which has snowballed to poor academic performance in agricultural science. It should be borne in our minds that the word “unqualified” in this context, may not necessarily connote not possessing the appropriate certificate meant for the teaching job’, however, it may be anchoring on professionalism.

The term school location connotes the position of the school within the chosen area of study. This may be rural or urban. Rural areas refer to villages and areas away from the local government headquarters, and lacking major amenities like healthcare centres, tarred road, electricity and pipe borne water. On the other hand, urban areas depict areas within the local government headquarters with the key amenities such as healthcare centres, tarred road, electricity and pipe borne water. Zudonu (2013) accentuated that our highly qualified teachers prefer to serve in urban areas than rural areas because of the presence of social amenities.

Researchers have compared rural students with students from urban schools on several major areas of academic achievement, including geography (Obasi, 2011), television technology (Umunadi, 2009), mathematics, science and reading (Ramos, Duque and Nieto, 2012; Ijenkeli, Paul, and Vershima, 2012; Reeves, 2012), level of stress (Tajularipin, Aminuddin, Vizata and Saifuddin, 2009) and senior school certificate examination (Adepoju and Oluchukwu, 2011). Although studies examining school’s location (urban or rural) on students’ educational outcomes started in the mid-80s in the United States, there appears to be no consensus on the significance of this characteristic (Ramos, Duque and Nieto 2012).

Academic performance is active rather than passive acquisition. Olamie (2012) defines academic performance as how students deal with their studies and how they cope with or accomplish different tasks given to them by teachers. According to Bilgin (2009), academic performance is a measure of the degree of success in performing specific tasks in a subject or area of study by students after a learning experience. It is the outcome of education that indicates how well a student or class of students are doing academically. Academic performance is a major issue to teachers, students, parents and guardians as well as other stakeholder in the education industry.

The question still remains is which of these teaching methods contribute to failure or success of students’ performance especially in developing countries like Nigeria where the causes of poor performance in secondary schools is not well understood. The major issue is that the usual conventional method has not been able to address the poor academic performance of students in agricultural science. A question could be asked at this point “would the use of inquiry method have any effect on students’ academic performance in agricultural science?” This was the gap that this study sought to empirically fill among Senior Secondary school in Adamawa state. Gender is also a crucial variable that will be considered in this study. Gender issue in Nigeria has become an issue of concern in some years back. As schools and educational institutions are more structured, gender difference takes up new and more focus of researchers. Gender relates to the difference in sex (that is, either male or female) and how this quality affects their dispositions and perception toward life and academic activities. (Mbaba, 2010) have shown that gender disparity is still very prevalent in Nigeria and perhaps the whole African countries. This is in line with the finding of Jimoh (2004) that male students performed better than female students in cognitive affect and psychomotor skill performance. This shows that there is a strong association between gender and response to science education. Okeke, (2007) sees gender as a socially/culturally constructed characteristics and roles, which are associated with males and females in any society. According to Okeke, it is different from sex which is a biological distinction in appearance (morphology) and function (physiology) as well as contributions of men and women. Some studies have shown

that male show superiority in performance than their female counterparts in agricultural science and physics. Cheung (2009) conducted a comprehensive review of the literature regarding gender issues related to agricultural science education. The study revealed that girls had a more favourable attitude towards studying agricultural science than did boys. In the other way round some studies (Okwor, Agu and Ukwuaba, 2006) have shown that there is no significant difference in the performance of males and females in agricultural science and physics. This study will indeed, verify the veracity of the claims of these authors.

Singh (2010) opines that gender refers to a socio-cultural construct that connotes the differentiated roles and responsibilities of men and women in a particular society. This definition implies that gender determines the roles which one plays in relation to general political, cultural, social and economic system of the society.

Statement of the Problem

School locations might determine students' performance in agricultural science. Based on observation by the researcher, there may be disparity in educational opportunities available to those who reside in rural or urban areas, because of disparity in distribution of educational facilities and material including personnel in favour of urban or rural schools.

Similarly, there is the issue of gender, defined as biased role expectation of culture and society, ascribed based on being males or females. Gender stereotyping continues to permeate our schools; and as it were, determines the academic performance of students. For example, some researchers revealed that there was no significant difference in the performance of male and female students in agricultural science while some studies observed significant difference in the student's academic performance. Udoh (2007) report zero effect of gender, maintaining that given the right condition and method of teaching to both male and female students, they will perform equally.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the effect of schools' location on academic performance of senior Secondary School Students Taught Agricultural Science using Inquiry Method in Adamawa State.

1. Determine the mean performance score of students in urban and rural schools as measured by Agricultural science Performance Test (ASPT).
2. Determine the mean performance score of male and female students taught with inquiry method as measured by Agricultural science Performance Test (ASPT).

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide this study.

1. What are the mean performance scores of agricultural science students Taught Agricultural Science using Inquiry Method in Adamawa State in urban and rural schools?
2. What are the mean performance scores of male and female agricultural science students taught with inquiry method?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of urban and rural students Taught Agricultural Science using Inquiry Method in Adamawa State.

2. HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female agricultural science students taught using inquiry method.

Methodology

The study adopted pretest-posttest quasi-experimental design. Quasi-experimental research is an empirical interventional study used to estimate the causal impact of an intervention on target population without random assignment (Dinardo, 2018). The area of the study is Adamawa State which was created on 29 August, 1991 out of the defunct Gongola state. Adamawa state is located at the north-eastern part of Nigeria. Adamawa state is geographically located at latitude 9.330 North and longitude 12.500 East. Population for the study comprised 115,497 students in Senior Secondary Schools (SSS II) who offered Agricultural Science subject in Adamawa State. The sample size that was used for the study was 20 intact classes which consist of 769 Senior Secondary School (SSS II) Students (416 male and 353 female; 425 Urban and 344 Rural; 390 Demonstration and 379 lecture) who offer Agricultural Science subjects. The instrument that was used for data collection in this study was Agricultural Science Performance Test (ASPT) developed by the researcher. It consists of 30 multiple-choice objective questions derived from the topics: (i) Ornamental Plants (ii) Weeds (iii) pests of crops and (iv) Diseases of Crops. Agricultural Science Performance Test (ASPT) was validated by three experts, from the Department of Vocational Education in Modibbo Adama University, Yola of Adamawa State. The instrument was pilot tested on SSS II students of Government Day Senior Secondary School, Herwagana, Gombe State, which was not part of the study area. This was to enable the researcher determine the workability of the instrument. The full reliability coefficient was determined using Cronbach alpha and a reliability coefficient 0.85 was obtained.

The researcher and research assistants (agricultural science teachers) in the 20 schools collected data for the study through pre-test and post-test using Agricultural Science Performance Test (ASPT). The data that was collected from the pre-test and post-test were analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1. What are the mean performance scores of agricultural science students’ Taught Agricultural Science using Inquiry Method in Adamawa State?

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation of performance scores of agricultural science students in urban and rural schools.

School Location	n	Pretest		Posttest		MD
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Urban	198	8.12	3.77	20.42	5.83	12.30
Rural	150	6.25	3.72	12.47	5.71	6.22

The descriptive statistics in Table 1 revealed that, an urban student in the inquiry method group with 198 students has a pretest mean score of 8.12 and standard deviation of 3.77. In the posttest males have the highest mean score of 20.42 with a standard deviation of 5.83. Rural students in the inquiry method group have 150 students with a mean score of 6.25 and standard deviation of 3.72 at pretest level and mean score of 12.47 with standard deviation of 5.71. The mean difference between pretest and posttest stands as 12.30 for urban students and 6.22 for rural students.

Research Question 2. What are the mean performance scores of male and female agricultural science students taught with inquiry method?

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation of performance scores of male and female agricultural science students taught with inquiry method.

Gender	n	Pretest		Posttest		MD
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	113	5.89	3.50	17.72	5.36	11.72
Female	105	6.64	3.92	17.86	5.84	11.22

The descriptive statistics in Table 2 revealed that, males in the inquiry method group with 113 students has a pretest mean score of 5.89 and standard deviation of 3.50. In the posttest males have the lowest mean score of 17.72 with a standard deviation of 5.36. Females in the inquiry method group has 105 students with a mean score of 6.64 and standard deviation of 3.92 at pretest level and mean score of 17.86 with standard deviation of 5.84. The mean difference between pretest and posttest stands as 11.72 for male inquiry method group and 11.22 for female inquiry method group.

Hypotheses Testing

The hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA at 0.05 level of significant.

HO1. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of urban and rural agricultural science students taught using inquiry method.

Table 3: ANCOVA of mean performance scores of urban and rural agricultural science students taught using inquiry method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Corrected Model	13757.701 ^a	2	6878.851	330.526	.000
Intercept	14651.526	1	14651.526	704.000	.000
PRETEST	6786.028	1	6786.028	326.066	.000
SCHOOL_LOCATION	7276.523	1	7276.523	349.634	.000
Error	11717.055	345	20.812		
Total	215396.000	348			
Corrected Total	25474.756	347			

a. R Squared = .540 (Adjusted R Squared = .538)

The results of the analysis in Table 3 shows that, there is significant difference between the mean performance scores of urban and rural agricultural science students taught using inquiry method $F = 349.63$ ($df 1, 345$), $P = 0.03$. Since the computed p-value (0.03) is less than 0.05 level of significant, therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected, and concluded that, there is significant difference between the mean performance scores of urban and rural agricultural science students taught using inquiry method.

HO2. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female agricultural science students taught using inquiry method.

Table 4: ANCOVA of mean performance scores of male and female agricultural science students taught using inquiry method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Corrected Model	2089.931 ^a	2	1044.965	47.955	.000
Intercept	8820.180	1	8820.180	404.774	.000
PRETEST_INQUIRY	2088.859	1	2088.859	95.861	.922
GENDER_INQUIRY	12.609	1	12.609	.579	.448
Error	4684.936	215	21.790		
Total	75725.000	218			
Corrected Total	6774.867	347			

a. R Squared = .308 (Adjusted R Squared = .302)

The results of the analysis in Table 4 shows that, there is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female agricultural science students taught using inquiry method $F = .58$ (df 1, 217), $P = 0.45$. Since the computed p-value (0.45) is greater than 0.05 level of significant, therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is upheld, and concluded that, there is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of agricultural science students taught with inquiry method.

Discussion of the Study

The findings of research question one indicates that there is a positive mean difference between the mean performance scores of urban and rural agricultural science students taught using inquiry method in favour of urban students. Owoeye and Yara (2011) in their studies on school location and academic performance of secondary school students in Ekiti State, Nigeria asserts that the various review of literature on school location influence on academic performance is not the same. While some maintain that urban students perform better in examinations than their rural counterparts, others found out that rural students (in spite of all odds) perform better. Some have submitted in their findings and concluded that no particular set up (urban or rural) can claim superiority over the other because their performances are the same. The findings of this study is similar to that, of Adesegun, Adekunle and Emmanuel (2016) who conducted a study on school location as correlates of students’ academic performance in Economics, the findings showed that schools located near border towns and places of economic interest distract students’ attention and researchers therefore concluded that in the future schools should not be located close to places of economic interest. This is because urban centres are better favoured with respect to distribution of social amenities such as pipe borne water, electricity, healthcare facilities while the rural areas are less favoured. This is also true in the distribution of educational facilities and teachers.

Contrarily, Onah and Ugwu (2010) in their study to determine the factors which predict performance in secondary school Physics in Ebonyi North educational Zone of Ebonyi State, asserted that the influence of school location on the performance in secondary school physics was not significant, hence, they concluded that school location does not influence physics performance of students in secondary school.

Findings of research question two revealed that there is a positive mean difference between the mean performance scores of male and female agricultural science students taught using inquiry method in favor of the females. Its corresponding hypotheses revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female agricultural science students taught using inquiry method. This finding is in contrast with Nnenna and Adukwu (2018) who

showed that there was a significant difference in the mean performance score of male and female students; male students achieved higher than their female counterparts in Biology Performance Test. Ransford, Shouqi, Frema, Offei, Junping and Ansah (2016) indicated that gender had no significant influence on students' attitude towards the learning of agricultural science. Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) reviewed that there are significant different in the mean performance of secondary school students in Agricultural Science based on gender. Anyaegbu, Irebuisi and Onyeyiri (2016) showed that there is significant difference between the academic performance of boys and girls in agricultural science, the male students performed better than female students.

Contrarily, in a study conducted by Anyaegbu, Irebuisi and Onyeyiri (2016) on gender differences in the academic performances of students in agricultural science in secondary schools in Isu local government area of Imo State, showed that, there is significant difference between the academic performance of boys and girls in agricultural science, the male students performed better than female students. Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) conducted a study to determine the effect of gender and academic performance of secondary school students in social studies in Abakaliki Urban of Ebonyi State, revealed that the mean performance score of female secondary school students was higher than the mean performance scores of male students. The findings of the study also revealed that; male and female secondary school students taught Agricultural Science by male teachers obtained higher mean scores than male and female students taught Agricultural Science by female teachers and female students taught social studies by male teacher performed better than masculine students taught Agricultural Science by male teacher and vice versa. The study also reviewed that there is significant difference in the mean performance of secondary school students in Agricultural Science based on gender. Nnenna and Adukwu (2018) conducted a study on the influence of gender senior secondary school student's performance in biology in Agbani Education Zone of Enugu State, found out significant difference in the mean performance score of male and female students, male students achieved higher than their female counterparts in Biology Performance Test.

Recommendations

From the result of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Urban and Rural schools should organize workshops and seminars internally which will enable teachers and their students to share ideas on the skills of inquiry teaching method.
2. Symposium and workshops should be organized and made compulsory for practicing teachers to inculcate skills in organizing and memorizing several inquiry teaching strategies that would equally benefit both the male and female gender.

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